

From Long Contexts to Short Windows: Fine-tuning Transformer on Short EEG Windows to Enable Real-time Neonatal Seizure Detection

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Abstract

Neonatal seizures are a global challenge and represent a significant neurological condition. Identifying and monitoring abnormal electrical activity in the brain is crucial for determining when a seizure occurs and for detecting the ongoing repetition or periodicity in electroencephalography (EEG), which is often performed by clinical experts and is time-consuming. The use of automated algorithms and deep learning convolutional neural networks (CNNs) has demonstrated significant progress and improved performance. However, CNNs frequently struggle to capture long-range dependencies, prompting the development of hybrid solutions that combine both local and global temporal modeling. Furthermore, despite using various window lengths, epoch sizes, and sampling frequencies in existing neonatal seizure detection models, several challenges limit the feasibility and effectiveness of detecting seizures with short EEG windows. These challenges include variability in EEG patterns, the non-stationary nature of EEG signals, artifacts and noise, subtle or non-convulsive seizures, imbalanced data, the absence of standardized EEG features, limited labeled data, and the necessity for generalization across different EEG systems. Additionally, reproducibility remains a significant obstacle, as many studies lack transparency and provide incomplete details. In this study, we adapt the hybrid Conformer and transformer through fine-tuning on neonatal EEG datasets to utilize their integrated local-global feature learning capabilities in short neonatal seizure EEG windows from multi-channel EEG recordings, thereby bridging the gap between long-context neural models and low-latency clinical applications. To promote open science and reproducibility of the neonatal EEG seizure detection model, we have released the full codebase, pre-trained models, and experiment configurations on GitHub under an open-source license. The findings from each model experiment, using the

original dataset, the synthetic minority over-sampling technique (SMOTE), and cost-sensitive learning, yielded promising results, with the highest AUC achieved using SMOTE. Overall, our work represents a first step towards fine-tuning the transformer model using short EEG windows to enable real-time monitoring and detection. However, the model’s performance is limited to the neonatal intensive care unit dataset from Helsinki University Hospital, highlighting the need for comprehensive experiments using various datasets in future research.

Keywords: Epileptic seizures, Seizure detection, EEG, Transformer, EEG Conformer, Neonatal seizure detection, Short EEG Windows

1 Introduction

Neonatal seizures are a worldwide challenge and neurological condition, occurring in 1 to 5.5 per 1,000 live births [1]. The World Health Organization defines neonatal seizures as *“paroxysmal events occurring during the neonatal period that are characterized by abnormal, excessive, and synchronous electrical discharges in the brain”*[2]. These seizures represent a critical clinical phenomenon in newborns that requires careful evaluation, diagnosis, and management, including early diagnosis and monitoring of seizures to enable timely medical intervention and impact on the long-term neurodevelopmental outcomes of infants [3, 4]. This process typically employs electroencephalography (EEG) to record and analyze brainwave patterns, which is regarded as the gold standard for diagnosing neonatal seizures [5]. Therefore, identifying and monitoring abnormal electrical activity in the brain helps determine when a seizure occurs and detects the evolving repetition or periodicity in the EEG, where the *“ictal event is characterized by the appearance of sudden, repetitive, evolving stereotyped waveforms with a definite beginning, middle, and end, lasting an (arbitrary)”* [6, 7].

Studies have been conducted to examine the manifestation of neonatal electrographic seizures, showing remarkable progress and performance. Neonatal seizure detection has evolved from automated methods [8–10] and classical machine learning techniques [11], which utilize statistical, frequency, and time-frequency domain features, to deep learning. Notably, the Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) approach has achieved state-of-the-art performance in automated feature extraction, detection, and classification [12–16]. Furthermore, the transformer model, recognized for its “attention mechanisms”, has been applied in seizure detection to capture long-range dependencies crucial for modeling the complex temporal dynamics of EEG signals [17–19]. Recently, a hybrid approach was developed that combines CNNs and Transformers to leverage the strengths of CNNs in extracting local features (segments of the EEG signal) while utilizing those features to capture long-range dependencies (larger portions of the EEG signal) [20]. These approaches have gained interest, primarily because CNNs struggle to explore the long-range temporal dependencies of EEG, which are essential for identifying seizure patterns. To address this shortfall, a transformer model was employed to capture long-range dependencies and learn about

the various relationships among different parts of the EEG signal, excelling at understanding the global context. Additionally, a variety of transformer-based foundation models have recently been released for EEG analysis and classification [21].

Despite advances in neural decoding, most existing seizure detection models rely on long temporal windows to capture spectral and temporal dependencies, underscoring the need for approaches that perform reliably on short windows. However, enabling real time epilepsy monitoring and early detection necessitates minimizing the gap between seizure identification and its onset to promote timely intervention and reduce complications, thereby enhancing its relevance in clinical settings. Existing attempts have utilized differing window lengths (most commonly 8 to 32 seconds, with few or none at 1 or 2 seconds) and sampling frequencies (32- 256 Hz) to create seizure detection models and reduce computational overload [10, 12, 14]. These approaches rely on classical machine learning methods (e.g., support vector machines (SVM)) or convolutional neural network (CNN)-based models. However, there have been limited to no attempts to evaluate transformer-based architectures for neonatal EEG seizure detection using short windows fit for real-time and low-latency inference. Moreover, although the majority of techniques utilize open-source EEG seizure datasets, the corresponding code and experimental pipelines are often not publicly available, and reproducibility is rarely validated. Our goals are to fine-tune transformer and Conformer models specifically for short EEG windows, while ensuring reproducibility through open-source code, standardized preprocessing pipelines, and publicly available pretrained models following open science practices, and to integrate this with data balancing strategies (SMOTE and cost-sensitive learning) to enhance the detection of neonatal seizures. In summary, shorter window sizes offer a beneficial trade-off between sensitivity and computational efficiency, while larger window sizes preserve critical EEG features, which necessitates extended EEG monitoring and expert interpretation. Consequently, real-time detection of neonatal seizures necessitates ultra-fast detection methods within a shorter time frame to minimize latency and allow for near-instantaneous intervention.

However, the feasibility and effectiveness of short EEG window seizure detection face challenges due to variability in EEG patterns, the non-stationary nature of EEG signals, artifacts and noise, subtle or non-convulsive seizures, imbalanced data, a lack of standardized EEG features, limited labeled data, the complexity of multichannel EEG (as seizures may manifest differently across channels), and the need for generalization across different EEG systems [22–25]. Overall, this study aims to learn useful representations of seizure and non-seizure events from short EEG windows, enabling more effective analysis and processing for real-time EEG monitoring and detection. Specifically, we investigate the following: (1) fine-tuning transformer-based architectures for short EEG windows, enabling ultra-fast neonatal seizure detection, (2) systematically evaluating SMOTE and cost-sensitive learning strategies on the neonatal seizure EEG dataset, (3) demonstrating the feasibility of transformer models for low-latency neonatal seizure detection, and (4) ensuring the experimental pipeline can be verified and reused by releasing all code, preprocessing pipelines, trained models, and evaluation scripts.

Fig. 1: Neonatal EEG preprocessing workflow. Step 1 - Data Loader & Preprocessing, Step 2 -Epoch Creation, Step 3 -Epoch Extraction, and Step 4 -Data Aggregation

2 Methods

2.1 Data Sources

We used the neonatal EEG dataset from the Neonatal intensive care unit at the Helsinki University Hospital [26] which contains a total of 79 neonatal EEG recordings, which are available freely in raw European data format files with their annotation files. The neonatal EEG data were selected for this study according to predefined inclusion criteria. Only those containing expert-verified annotations of seizure events were included, while any neonatal EEG datasets without seizure annotations were excluded.

2.2 Data Preprocessing Pipeline

We used Python MNE and Brain-decode to preprocess [27, 28] the neonatal EEG and the processed raw EEG were saved as .fif for future reference and analysis. As shown in Fig. 1, a set of steps was conducted: (I). Raw EEG selection and standardization were conducted to generate consistent raw signals, including uniform channel names and coherence across the EDF files, (II) Bipolar Montage: A bipolar montage was created based on the 10-20 system and 18 channels generated from electrode pairs, (III) Downsampling: The original sampling frequency of the EEG recordings was set to 256 Hz and downsampled to 64Hz, (IV) Bandpass Filtering: Finally, preprocessed EEG data from an EDF file with bandpass (0.3-30 Hz), notch (50 Hz), and custom filter coefficients were applied based on [10], (V) Epoch Creation: The continuous neonatal raw EEG dataset was segmented into epochs based on expert annotations, with each epoch representing a specific time window. This segmentation aligns with the temporal nature of seizure events and was established using a 1-second window from the continuous EEG signal. The experts provided one-second resolution annotations for EEG non-seizure or seizure events. Utilizing the annotations from the three

experts, a dataset containing variables such as "experts, infant ID, seizure durations, seizure start times in seconds, seizure end times in seconds, seizure start samples, and seizure end samples" was created. This dataset was a reference for determining and constructing fixed time window epochs based on one-second expert annotation markers. The agreement among all three experts was the primary inclusion criterion, (VI) Normalization was applied to handle non-stationary behavior, mitigating variability, and enhancing the model's ability to learn relevant patterns, and (VII) Data Aggregation and Preparation for Transformer-based Datasets: Labels corresponding to seizure and non-seizure periods were assigned based on event annotations, saved NumPy format and ready for model training.

2.3 Model Architecture

EEG Conformer [20] and a custom variant architecture for a neonatal EEG transformer were set up to fine-tune the neonatal seizure detection model using short EEG windows. On the one hand, the EEG Conformer [20] introduced a significant advancement over traditional feature-based methods for EEG analysis, offering end-to-end learning that automatically extracts discriminative features from preprocessed EEG data. To handle short windows, we adjusted positional embeddings, attention mechanisms, and convolutional kernels to maintain spectral-temporal feature extraction despite limited temporal context. On the other hand, we trained a neonatal EEG transformer-only variant model for neonatal seizure detection based on multichannel EEG signals to capture complex spatial-temporal dynamics. The neonatal transformer model employs an encoder-like structure to process the neonatal EEG input sequence through input and preprocessing, positional encoding, multiple layers of multi-head attention and feedforward networks, residual connections and layer normalization, and classifier.

2.4 Implementation and Model Training

This study utilizes the EEGConformer and Custom Transformer and does not retrain the CNN baseline on the neonatal EEG dataset. Instead, we adopt EEGConformer as an informed baseline based on its established state-of-the-art results [20]. The model was trained using the original imbalanced dataset, the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) [29, 30], and cost-sensitive learning (CSL) [31–33]. In CSL, the class weights were computed, and the inverse frequency method was used to assign higher weights to the minority class, helping the model avoid bias toward the majority class. All model variants were trained using a binary classification with 18 channels and 64Hz. Cross-entropy loss was used to measure the difference between predicted probabilities and actual labels. The Adam optimizer was employed for its adaptive learning rate capabilities, set at an initial rate of 0.001. The model underwent training for 50, 100, 300, and 500 epochs, each consisting of a forward pass, loss computation, and backward propagation. Filter time length, pool time length, and pool time stride were adjusted to 16, 8, and 4, while default values were used for the other parameters. Further information on the workflow illustrating the preprocessing of short EEG windows, followed by fine-tuning, classification, and evaluation of neonatal EEG is presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Workflow for Fine-Tuning Transformer from Long-Context Representations to Short EEG Window Neonatal Seizure Detection

2.5 Reproducibility and Open Science

All data preprocessing pipelines, model architectures, training scripts, and evaluation tools used in this study are openly available at Github ¹ to promote transparency and reproducibility.

2.6 Evaluation

During training, we monitored the training and validation loss and accuracy to ensure proper generalization. This included loss and accuracy trajectories over training epochs, ROC curves with area under the curve (AUC) metrics, and confusion matrices with detailed classification metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. The model’s performance was assessed using the following metrics: accuracy, which is the proportion of correctly classified epochs out of the total number of epochs; sensitivity (recall), or the model’s ability to identify seizure epochs correctly; specificity, referring to the model’s ability to correctly identify non-seizure epochs; precision, which is the proportion of true positive seizure detections among all positive detections; and F1 score, the harmonic mean of precision and recall that provides a balance between the two. Furthermore, for each approach and window length, we evaluated the performance by computing latency per EEG window and seizure detection delay relative to onset.

3 Results

Out of the 79 neonatal recordings, the study included only 39, accounting for 60 hours and 6 minutes of neonates with seizures. The EEG Conformer achieved an

¹https://github.com/gel1has3/NeonatalSeizureDetection_ShortEEG.Windows

Table 1: Experimental Results

Metrics	EEG Conformer			Custom Transformer		
	Original	SMOTE	CSL	Original	SMOTE	CSL
AUC	.87	.92	.88	.82	.88	.82
Precision	.92	.74	.81	.75	.82	.43
Recall	.40	.92	.51	.41	.77	.67
F1-Score	.58	.82	.63	.53	.79	.52

AUC of .87, .92, and .88 on the original (imbalanced dataset), SMOTE, and CSL. Whereas, the custom transformer resulted in .82, .88, and .82 on the imbalanced dataset, SMOTE, and CSL respectively. The highest AUC was observed in SMOTE in both the EEG Conformer and Custom Transformer. After the employment of SMOTE and Transformer the value of recall and F1-score increased as shown in Table 1. Figures 3 and 4 display the experimental results of the EEG Conformer and Transformer, featuring training and validation accuracy and loss, along with the ROC curves.

3.1 Performance Comparison Across Models

Despite the custom transformer achieving competitive results, the EEG Conformer attained a higher AUC (0.890 ± 0.026) compared to the custom transformer’s AUC (0.840 ± 0.03). The EEG Conformer technique exhibits a higher F1-score (0.677 vs. 0.613) and a somewhat slightly lower recall (0.610 vs. 0.617) than the custom transformer-only model. Overall, the high performance of the EEG Conformer model on short EEG windows can be attributed to its inherent ability to capture both local and global temporal patterns through the fusion of convolutional and attention mechanisms. In contrast, the custom transformer, which relies on self-attention, lacks the necessary inductive bias to extract subtle, short-range neonatal EEG features, leading to underperformance in limited-duration contexts. Additional details are presented in Table 2. Furthermore, Fig. 5a presents a bar chart that compares the accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and AUC of the EEG conformer and custom transformer. Each bar represents the mean value across three experimental runs (Original Dataset, SMOTE, Cost-Sensitive Learning). The EEG conformer generally exhibits smaller error bars compared to the custom transformer, indicating more stable and reliable performance.

3.2 EEG Conformer Performance Comparison Based on 1-, 2-, and 4-Second EEG Windows

Fig. 5b illustrates the performance comparison across different evaluation metrics (Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-Score, and AUC) for three models: Original, SMOTE, and CSL. The mean scores are shown with error bars representing the standard deviation. The results indicate that error bars suggest greater variability in CSL performance, while the results for SMOTE are more stable. The accuracy and AUC for short EEG window durations (1s, 2s, 4s) show that while the overall trends are similar, the original maintains high Accuracy, and SMOTE maintains high AUC, F1 Score,

Table 2: Performance metrics with mean \pm standard deviation and 95% confidence intervals for EEG Conformer and Custom Transformer techniques

Metric	EEG Conformer (mean \pm std)	Custom Transformer (mean \pm std)	EEG Conformer (95% CI)	Custom Transformer (95% CI)
AUC	0.890 \pm 0.026	0.840 \pm 0.035	[0.824, 0.956]	[0.754, 0.926]
Precision	0.823 \pm 0.091	0.667 \pm 0.208	[0.598, 1.049]	[0.150, 1.183]
Recall	0.610 \pm 0.274	0.617 \pm 0.186	[-0.071, 1.291]	[0.155, 1.078]
F1-Score	0.677 \pm 0.127	0.613 \pm 0.153	[0.362, 0.991]	[0.233, 0.994]

Fig. 3: The EEG Conformer Training and Validation Accuracy and Loss, along with ROC Curves. a, b, and c, display the training and validation accuracy, training and validation loss, and ROC curves based on the original neonatal EEG datasets. d, e, and f present the SMOTE experimentation results for training and validation accuracy, training and validation loss, and ROC curves, respectively. g,h,and i illustrate the cost-sensitive learning outcomes for training and validation accuracy, training and validation loss, and ROC curves, respectively.

Precision, and Recall across all experimental settings (Fig. 5). CSL achieved notable improvements in F1-score, precision, and recall over the original model, reflecting its effectiveness in addressing class imbalance by directly weighting misclassification costs. Although it underperformed compared to SMOTE. Furthermore, across the three class-balancing strategies and window configurations, we observed an average latency of 0.019 ± 0.000 seconds for 1-second windows and 0.021 ± 0.002 seconds for 4-second windows.

Fig. 4: Custom Transformer Training and Validation Accuracy and Loss, as well as the ROC Curves. a, b, and c, show the training and validation accuracy, training and validation loss, and ROC curves on the original neonatal EEG datasets. d, e, and f illustrate the SMOTE experimentation results for training and validation accuracy, training and validation loss, and ROC curves, respectively. g, h, and i demonstrate the cost-sensitive learning outcomes for training and validation accuracy, training and validation loss, and ROC curves, respectively.

Fig. 5: a) A bar chart with error bars (standard deviation) comparing EEG Conformer and Custom Transformer across metrics. b) The bar chart with error bars based mean, standard deviation, and 95% confidence intervals for each metric across the models Original, SMOTE, and CSL

4 Discussions

In this study, a hybrid Conformer and a custom transformer were finetuned and trained for neonatal seizure detection using short EEG windows. As shown in [20], the original EEG conformer achieved remarkable results on different EEG datasets and observed that the transformer incorporated into CNN to learn global dependencies in the temporal domain was a promising approach. To further assess its adaptability in neonatal

seizure classification, the EEG conformer neonatal seizure detection model was experimented on a neonatal EEG dataset under three experimental conditions: baseline (original class distribution), SMOTE, and CSL techniques. Furthermore, the custom transformer was further tested on short EEG windows to explore its sensitivity to brief neonatal EEG seizure detection.

The neonatal seizure detection model was trained using a consensus-labeled dataset and created using the common features derived from the overlapping annotations of the three experts. The model achieved promising and competitive results on a neonatal EEG dataset using short EEG windows. The EEG Conformer AUC is approximately 87-92% for EEG data utilizing a short epoch or window length of one second, which is higher than the custom transformer. Overall, despite the custom transformer achieving competitive results, the EEG Conformer attained a higher average accuracy (0.857 ± 0.049) and AUC (0.890 ± 0.026) compared to the custom transformer’s accuracy (0.817 ± 0.047) and AUC (0.840 ± 0.03). The EEG Conformer technique exhibits a higher F1-score (0.677 vs. 0.613) and a slightly lower recall (0.610 vs. 0.617) than the custom transformer-only model. Our experimental findings strongly support, and a promising and competitive performance was achieved in the neonatal EEG dataset based on short EEG windows. The outcomes of the hybrid EEG Conformer demonstrate its ability to transfer learned representations and adapt to new patient populations or clinical settings with minimal reconfiguration. The EEG Conformer learns localized patterns and long-range temporal dependencies to enable neonatal seizure detection. However, in the current literature, CNNs have dominated the state-of-the-art neonatal seizure detection, owing to their strength in capturing local temporal and spatial patterns. This local inductive bias has made CNNs the foundation of many leading approaches. Nonetheless, seizures often display complex temporal dynamics that extend over longer periods, which CNNs with limited receptive fields may struggle to capture effectively. Conversely, Transformer-based models are well-suited for modeling global temporal dependencies. Still, they tend to perform poorly on EEG data due to their lack of locality bias and the large amount of EEG seizure data required. Overall, hybrid architectures that combine CNNs with Transformer-like self-attention mechanisms, such as Conformers, offer a promising balance: they retain the ability of CNNs to extract detailed local features while benefiting from the long-range temporal modeling capabilities of Transformers.

Furthermore, to ensure real-time seizure detection, an optimal windowing strategy balances capturing immediate, fine-grained seizure features with integrating broader temporal context to improve overall classification accuracy and reduce false positives. For example, adaptive windowing strategies optimize the detection of specific features like spikes by dynamically adjusting window lengths to match the signal’s characteristics. Moreover, future research and successful clinical implementation should prioritize generalizability, optimize false alarm rates, enhance interpretability through explainable AI, conduct rigorous long-term validation, integrate multimodal data, and develop patient-specific models.

This study has several limitations. First, the evaluation was based on a neonatal intensive care unit EEG dataset from Helsinki University Hospital, which may not represent the full range of EEG signals across wider patient populations, thereby limiting

the broad applicability of the findings. Hyperparameter tuning was done conservatively to ensure fairness among models, but more aggressive tuning might change their relative performance. Latency and detection delays were estimated during validation (or testing) in an offline setting, not in real-time streaming EEG systems. Lastly, we recognize that clinical deployment will require prospective validation, interpretability analysis, and robustness testing across different acquisition settings, all of which are important directions for future work. Furthermore, our evaluation is limited to the EEGConformer and Custom Transformer models, using EEGConformer’s previously demonstrated superior performance as an informed baseline, while comprehensive CNN comparisons are designated for future investigation.

5 Conclusions

The study aimed to detect neonatal seizure and non-seizure events from short EEG windows. This study provides complete information (code and data preprocessing steps) to promote open science and reproducibility, addressing a significant barrier to scientific transparency and progress. The study focuses exclusively on neonates experiencing seizures, including only 39 of the 79 cases. The raw neonatal EEG underwent preprocessing, creating and preparing 1-second segment window EEG epochs for transformer modeling training and fine-tuning. Any 1-second segment that did not align with the three experts’ agreement was excluded from the model training. Following that, we fine-tune the transformer model to learn useful representations of seizure and non-seizure patterns from multi-channel EEG with the original dataset, SMOTE, and cost-sensitive learning, yielding promising results. Overall, our work represents a first step toward fine-tuning the transformer model using short EEG windows. However, the model’s performance is limited to the neonatal intensive care unit dataset from Helsinki University Hospital. Therefore, a crucial next step is to fine-tune the model and conduct experiments using cross-border or multi-institutional datasets. This would enable validation in diverse, real-world settings and provide a robust assessment of its generalizability and practical effectiveness.

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